

Effect of Service Culture on Service Innovation Capability in the Telecommunication Industry

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Abstract

The service sector has steadily become a key factor in the growth of an economy and the competitiveness has increasingly changed the business environment in which an organisation operates. This, however, has challenged organisations to improve their capability to innovate in order to stay ahead in the competitive business environment. However, most firms embed in a service culture that influences the service quality, customer's expectation and employees' delivery to customers. The purpose of this research is to investigate the influence of service culture on service innovation capability. A sample of 124 questionnaires from the employees in the telecommunication industry was collected. PLS-SEM analysis was used to determine the effect of service culture on service innovation capability. The result revealed that service culture has a strong and significant effect on service innovation capability. In addition, the result shows that clan culture has the most contributing effect on service innovation capability than other cultural types. The importance-performance matrix analysis (IPMA) results further explained that market and hierarchy culture need to be given priority. The findings suggest that having the right service culture unifies its focus on excellent service, commitment to quality, improved employee behaviour and employees' attention to details. This gives the organisation the ability to develop service innovation capability.

Keywords: Service culture, Service innovation capability, Telecommunication industry

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1. Introduction

In this era of globalization, the competitive challenges have increasingly changed the business environment an organisation operates. These challenges such as technological development, customers' requirements, new markets and competitor's knowledge made organisations exert themselves to develop their innovation capability to succeed (Aljanabi, 2020; Saunila & Ukko, 2012). Innovation capability is the main reason for continued development in which organisations apply their skills, resources and knowledge towards new or existing product or services, marketing, management and processes (Hogan, 2011). This shows that innovation capability is embedded in the work practice and process of an organisation (Yang, Nguyen & Le, 2018). It allows the

organisation to attune to the business environment, market and competition resulting to growth and competitive advantage (Saunila & Ukko, 2012; Yang et al., 2018). Organisations that engage in innovation capability are mostly instituted in a culture. Service culture is a vital and powerful factor functioning in any organisation. It influences the service quality, customer's expectation and employee delivery to customers (Adebayo, Worlu, Moses & Ogunnaike, 2020; Zerbe, Dobni & Harel, 1998). Service culture makes known the processes that goes in the organisation that is, what the employees are expected to do and their ability to contribute to the organisation (Martins, 1992; Webster, 1990). Understanding service culture is important factor in influencing the innovation capability of an organisation (Imron et al., 2021; Nguyen, Phong & Hui, 2019).

Scholars have studied the link between organisational culture and innovation (Abiola-Falemu, Ogunsemi & Oyediran, 2010; Tian, Deng, Zhang & Salmader, 2018); innovation capability (Adelekan, 2016; Cakar & Erturk, 2010; Oreagba et al., 2023) creativity and innovation (Martins & Martins, 2002; Martins & Terblanche, 2003); service quality (Luk, 1997). Tian et al. (2018) contributes that the study culture is not isolated, thus, there is need to consider the effect of culture in an organisation. Martins (1992) explains that culture can affect the level of service provided by employees in an organisation. This, in turn can affect their capability to be innovative in the organisation. Furthermore, Luk (1997) and Webster (1990) note that the study of service culture is somewhat limited, thus this study wants to empirically investigate the influence of service culture on service innovation capability. However, since service culture is from a service perspective, this study intends to bring new insight by focusing on the telecommunication industry in Nigeria. This study aims to focus on the top players in the telecommunication industry, which are 9mobile, Airtel, MTN and GLO. The main objective of the study is to investigate the influence of service culture on service innovation capability in the Telecommunication industry in Nigeria.

From this study, the following implications explains that service culture encourages open communication, creativity and innovation, and organisational learning which the telecommunication industry should adopt in order to improve innovation capability of employees in the organisation.

2. Literature Review

2.1 *Service Culture*

Service culture can be traced from the paradigm of organisational culture, which is also referred to as corporate culture. It is one of the important aspects to the functioning of an organisation. It defines the way an organisation conducts its business in terms of the processes and outcomes (Mohammed & Bardai, 2012; Motilewa, Worlu, Agboola & Adeniji, 2016; Tian et al., 2018). Scholars (Marcoulides & Heck, 1993; Szydlo & Grzes-Buklaho, 2020; Schein, 1990) have widely studied organisational culture, leading to numerous definitions. Amongst them, the work of Schein (1990) has been notable by most scholars in their various research fields. Schein (1990) described culture as “a pattern of basic assumptions that a given group has invented, discovered or developed in learning to cope with its problems of external adaption and internal integration, and have worked well enough to be considered valid and, therefore, to be taught to new members as the correct way to think and feel about these problems” (p. 111). Scholarly reviews (Luk, 1997; Hogan et al., 2011; Webster, 1990) on the definitions of culture have begun to recognize the importance of organisational culture in service marketing because it influences employees and customers. The delivery of service brings the employees and customers together, thus, there is need for established

procedure and processes for service employees in the organisation so that the service employees would have similar perception of the organisational setting (Dikmen & Bozdoglar, 2017; Webster, 1990). In terms of service culture, Gronroos (as cited in Zerbe et al., 1998) explained service culture as “a culture where an appreciation for good service exists and giving good service to internal as well as external customer is considered a natural way of life and one of the most important norms by everyone” (p.168). They explained further that service provided is mostly interacted between the employees and customers (Gronroos, 1990; Oyedokun, & Adeolu-Akande, 2022). Thus, service culture communicates to employees how to respond to new or unforeseen challenges with customers and be service-oriented (Ahmed & Rafiq, 2003). This explains that service culture influences the way employee do things within the organisation and what differentiates its service from other organisational service delivery and overall work practices.

For this research, service culture influences the behaviour and mindset of employees in an organisation to be service-oriented (Dikmen & Bozdoglar, 2017; Gronroos, 1990; Adeolu-Akande, & Oyedokun, 2022). Thus, we focus on the employee’s perception on service culture.

In addition, service managers need to understand the cultural type that exist in the organisation in order to cultivate such attributes when necessary. The competing values model (CVM) has received a lot of attention in recent years as it is generally used in many empirical studies (Adelekan, 2016; Rezaei et al., 2018) (see Fig 1). CVM is an analytical tool that is used to classify the different cultural types that exist in an organisation (Cameron and Quinn, 1999) and also interpret its effect on innovation capability it in this research.

2.2 *Service Innovation Capability*

Innovation capability is an important element of an innovative organisation. It is the fundamental source for firm’s success, superior performance and competitive advantage (Saunila, 2020). Rangone, (1999) refers to “innovation capability as the company’s ability to develop new products and processes, and to achieve superior technological and management performance” (p. 235). Lawson and Samson (2001) pinpoint that “innovation capability is the ability to continuously transform knowledge and ideas into new products, processes and systems for the benefits of the firm and stakeholders” (p. 384). Oreagba et al. (2023) explains that innovation capability relates to market needs, knowledge, product, process and technology.

However, the approach to innovation used by manufacturing companies to innovation is not directly applicable or transferred to service organisations (Hogan Soutar McColl-Kennedy & Sweeney, 2011; Lillis, Szwejczewski & Goffin, 2015). This is as a result of the nature of services, that is, intangibility, variability, heterogeneity and inseparability and innovation capability is interwoven with the service process, service product and routines of the organisation (Lillis et al., 2015). Zhang and Hartley (2018) contribute that “service innovation capability is the organisation’s ability to gather information and create knowledge to develop and implement new products, process and services” (p.75). Lillis et al. (2015) defines service innovation capability “as the ability of the organisations to adapt the service process to the changing environment” (p.50). Hogan et al. (2011) defines “service innovation capability as the firm’s ability relative to its competitors, to apply the collective knowledge, skills, and resources to innovation activities relating to new products, processes, services, or management, marketing or work organization

systems, to create added value for the firm or its stakeholders” (p.1255). In other words, service innovation capability is the ability of the organisation to gather information, apply knowledge, skills and other competencies to develop existing or new products, services, marketing and work processes to attune to the changing environment and achieve superior performance and competitive advantage (Lillies et al., 2015; Hogan et al., 2011; Zhang & Hartley, 2018; Adeolu-Akande, Oyedokun, & Oyedokun, 2023).

Fig 1: The competing values Framework Source: Cameron and Quinn (1999)

2.3 Service Culture and Innovation Capability

Service culture is resource that has impact on the strategic outcomes of the organisation. It is reviewed to have an impact on the work system whereby values such as teamwork, communication, respect, empowerment is introduced and enhanced in the organisation (Cakar & Erturk, 2010; Idiegeyan0ose, Opeke & Nwokeoma,2018). This tends to stimulate the behaviour among service employees thereby, affecting the organisation either positively or negatively (Cerovice, Kvasic & Cerovic, 2010; Marcoulides & Heck, 1993; Shein, 1990; Tian et al., 2018). Possessing the right cultural characteristic is a key component that enables the organisation have necessary capabilities to innovate. This enables the service employees to make effort to improve their capacity to innovate, achieve the objectives of the organisation, thereby leading to superior performance. Imron et al. (2020) note that service culture has a significant effect on innovation capability of an organisation.

However, intensely looking into each organisational cultural type, most of the is argued to affect

innovation capability. Adelekan (2016), Mohammed and Bardai (2012), Naranjo-Valencia, Jimenez- Jimenez and Sanz-Valle (2016) and Rezaei, Allameh and Ansari (2018) note that adhocracy has a strong effect on innovation capability while hierarchy culture has a weak impact on innovation culture. Rezaei et al. (2018) note that hierarchy and market culture acts as barriers to innovative activities.

Fig 2: A framework linking service culture and service innovation capability

3. Methodology

A survey instrument was adopted to gather data on the telecommunication employees from the top players in the industry- MTN, GLO, 9mobile and Airtel. The development of the survey instrument focused on a structured questionnaire to collect its data, and it was self-administered to 150 employees. Out of the 150 copies distributed to the employees, 124 copies were retrieved, which accounted for 83% response rate. The questionnaire used for this study is made up of three sections. The first section includes the variable for service culture. The second section focused on innovation capability. The third section includes the respondent’s demography data. 91.9 % were made up of staffs while 8.1% comprise of managers. 68% of the respondents were male while that of female were 56%. Furthermore, majority of the respondents (71%) had 3-5 years of experience while 46% had 1-2 years and 7% had above 6 years of work experience.

In line with the previous studies, innovation capability was measured using Hogan et al. (2011) measure of service innovation capability. This study adapted the instruments and used only eight (8) items to reflect marketing, client and technology-focused innovation capability. The items were measured using a 5-point scale ranging strongly disagree to strongly agree. Organisational culture was measured using Obendhain and Johnson (2004) and was adapted to entail twelve (12) items. Each item was measure using a 5-point scale which is similar to the measurement of innovation capability. The result from the reliability test confirmed that the analysis shows that the indicators for service innovation capability ($\alpha=0.948$; CR= 0.957; AVE=0.735) were consistent with the data. The result for service culture ($\alpha=0.907$; CR= 0.920; AVE=0.507) were also consistent with the data. The sub-variable for service culture, that is, adhocracy culture ($\alpha=0.760$; CR= 0.861; AVE=0.676), clan culture ($\alpha=0.788$; CR= 0.876; AVE=0.703), hierarchy culture ($\alpha=0.736$; CR=

0.849; AVE=0.652) and market culture ($\alpha=0.574$; CR= 0.741; AVE=0.511) were also consistent with the data (see Table 1).

The study used PLS-SEM to assess the model and determine the statistical significance. The T-value, p-values, path-coefficient and R2 was used to assess the model, service culture and service innovation capability. The bootstrapping model with β , p-values and T-values were used to determine the significant influence of the construct. This bootstrapping method was programmed to 5000 subsamples, which according to (), would improve the result of the hypothesis. The IPMA technique was also used in this study to reflect the level of importance and performance of service culture. It allows for identifying the most relevant areas that need specific actions.

Table 1: Synthesized Information About Measures of Variables

Construct	Cronbach Apha (α)	Reliability (CR)	AVE	Squared Correlation Matrix				
				ADH	CLAN	HIER	MKT	SINNV
Service Culture	0.907	0.920	0.507					
Adhocracy	0.760	0.861	0.676	0.823				
Clan	0.788	0.876	0.703	0.696	0.837			
Hierarchy	0.736	0.849	0.652	0.763	0.696	0.809		
Market	0.574	0.741	0.511	0.662	0.708	0.867	0.836	
Service Innovation Capability	0.948	0.957	0.735	0.523	0.750	0.597	0.610	0.857

Notes: Average Variance Extracted (AVE); Composite Reliability (CR); Adhocracy (ADH); Clan (CLAN); Hierarchy (HIER); Market (MKT); Service innovation capability (SINNV)

4. Results

Table 2: Relationship Between Customer Loyalty and Sustainable Market Performance

Parameters	Path Coefficient	Standard Deviation	T-Value	P-Value	R ²	Decision
Adhocracy -> Service Culture	0.282	0.017	16.915	0.000		
Clan -> Service Culture	0.332	0.034	9.818	0.000		
Hierarchy -> Service Culture	0.293	0.024	12.272	0.000		
Market-> Service Culture	0.212	0.013	16.234	0.000		
Adhocracy -> Service Innovation Capability	0.199	0.015	13.002	0.000		
Clan -> Service Innovation Capability	0.234	0.031	7.537	0.000		
Hierarchy-> Service Innovation Capability	0.206	0.020	10.509	0.000		
Market -> Service Innovation Capability	0.149	0.015	9.689	0.000		
H1 Service Culture -> Service innovation capability	0.704	0.050	13.971	0.000	0.49 6	Accepted

	Importance	Performance
Adhocracy Culture	0.270	84.223
Clan Culture	0.245	77.225
Hierarchy Culture	0.286	87.619
Market Culture	0.196	88.449

H1 predicts that there is a significant relationship between service culture and service innovation capability. Given that service culture components (i.e., adhocracy, clan, market and hierarchy culture) have a significant effect on service innovation capability. The result in Table 2 for the PLS-SEM model shows that 49.6 percent of the observed variable in service innovation capability is explained by the four sub-variables (R2= 0.496, Adjusted R2= 0.492). The coefficient for adhocracy culture ($\beta= 0.282$, $t= 16.915$, $P\text{-value}= 0.00$); clan culture ($\beta= 0.332$, $t= 9.760$, $P\text{-value}= 0.00$); market culture ($\beta= 0.212$, $t= 16.763$, $P\text{-value}= 0.00$); hierarchy culture ($\beta= 0.293$, $t= 12.317$, $P\text{-value}= 0.00$). This shows that clan culture is relatively stronger than other cultural types in explaining the changes in service innovation capability (see Table 2 and Figure 1-3). This indicates that H1 should be accepted. That is, service culture has a significant effect on service innovation capability in the telecommunication industry.

Table 2 further shows the IPMA, market culture has the highest performance, but it had the lowest important factor. It also shows that hierarchy culture has the highest important factor, but the performance factor is the second highest. However, the performance factor is followed by adhocracy and clan culture. The result indicate that hierarchy and market culture have more impact in terms of the importance and performance factor.

Fig 1: Structural Model with PLS-SEM

Fig 2. Bootstrapping of the β and P-values with PLS-SEM

Fig 3. Bootstrapping of the β and T-values with PLS-SEM

5. Discussion and Conclusion

In this paper, service culture and service innovation capability in the telecommunication industry was empirically evaluated. The study reviewed that service culture is a key component in the organisation, thus, having the right culture is vital to measure service employee's perception and behaviour of the organisation with respect to how deliver services to the customers.

This study provides strong empirical support that service culture has a significant influence on service innovation capability. It also revealed that clan, adhocracy, hierarchy and market culture have a positive and significant influence on innovation capability. The finding supports clan culture to contribute the most to service culture followed by hierarchy, market and adhocracy culture. Existing literature on organisational culture explained that the clan culture creates an environment where employees can easily share their ideas. Such organisation tends to have high involvement employees in terms of improving employee's satisfaction, internal service quality, employee productivity and retention; and high concern for customers in terms of customer satisfaction, service value and customer loyalty (Cameron & Quinn, 1999; Heskett, Jones, Loveman, Sasser & Schlesinger, 1994). Clan culture according to Obechain and Jonhson (2004) includes certain values such as teamwork, employee loyalty, and employee development. Adelekan (2016), Oney-Yazici et al. (2007) and Vincent et al. (2004) supports that clan culture is great resource for organisations to shape their employees' capability to innovate. This shows that the telecommunication industry emphasizes clan culture as their cultural values to the employees as the industry provides service to about 95million subscribers, which requires a large number of employees to manage the service provided (Pan Africa Capitol, 2013). Thus, cultivating the right cultural traits in the telecommunication industry can also be considered a resource because it unifies focus on excellent service, commitment to quality service, improved employee behaviour and employee's attention to details while providing service (Howard, 1998; Luk, 1997).

The findings from IPMA suggests that market and hierarchy culture is an important determinant to affect innovation capability in the telecommunication industry. Market culture emphasizes competitiveness, goal achievement and high productivity (Cameron & Quinn, 1999). This enables them to be result-oriented. Thus, there is need to adopt market culture in the departments that needs such culture in the telecommunication industry. This can contribute to the performance of the department such as the sales department in which they are expected to achieve a certain sale target, thus market culture is needed to improve the innovativeness of such department (Tian et al., 2018). Hierarchy culture focuses on a structured work environment, efficiency and cost minimization (Bardia, 2013). This tends to increase the importance of working in a formal organisation. However, scholars (Obenchain & Johnson, 2004; Valencia et al., 2010) note that such formal structures tend to affect the innovativeness in an organisation. Nevertheless, Edwards et al. (2002) argued that there is need for other cultural types to co-exist with the main culture- clan culture in order to withstand the pressure of innovation and other demands of the organisation.

6. Managerial Implication

From a managerial viewpoint, this paper has several implications. First, open communication should be encouraged in order to recognise and adopt employees' suggestions in terms of possible alternatives to improve the product, service, marketing, system and people in the organisation. Also, to build team trust amongst employees in the organisation. This would also improve employee's relationship to provide quality service to the customers. Second, there is need to foster an environment that encourage creativity and innovation in order to meet the changing demand of

the business environment at large. Services have unique features, thus, there is need to try new approach as that's what differentiates one's service from its competitors. This can be achieved through training and development programs, group creativity, learning processes and other multidisciplinary approaches developed by the organisation. As a result, the employees would be considered as a competitive advantage with the capability of being effective and competence in their service offering. Third, managers should be flexible to learn from the employee and create a climate that would embrace their skills and knowledge in order to transform or improve into new or existing product or service and marketing such as advertisement, sales programs, product distribution, and product quality. This would enable the organisation achieve competitive advantage compared to its competitors, and also help the employees to innovatively meet customer's demand and providing quality service.

7. Limitation and Future Research

This study was conducted using a single research method that is, quantitative research method. Thus, multi-research methods, that is, combination of both quantitative and qualitative research method can be considered for further studies. The study focused on the top players in the telecommunication industry, there is need to considered other players in the industry.

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References

- Abiola-Falemu, J. O., Ogunsemi, D. R., & Oyediran, O. S. (2010, May). Assessment of organisational culture and innovation practices of construction companies in Southwest Nigeria. In CIB Task Group and Working Commission, P. Barret et al.,(ed) TG59 & W112-Special Track 18th CIB World Building Congress (pp. 218-33).
- Adebayo, O. P., Worlu, R. E., Moses, C. L., & Ogunnaike, O. O. (2020). An Integrated Organisational Culture for Sustainable Environmental Performance in the Nigerian Context. *Sustainability*, 12(20), 8323. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12208323>
- Adelekan, S. A. (2016). The impact of organizational culture on innovation capability of SMEs. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, 4, 9.
- Adeolu-Akande, M.A & Oyedokun, G.E. (2022). An Appraisal of Effectiveness of Information Communication Technology in Office Management in the COVID-19 Era. *International Journal of Business and Management Invention (IJBMI)*, vol. 11(03), 2022, pp. 28-44. Journal DOI- 10.35629/8028
- Adeolu-Akande, M.A., Oyedokun, D.M, & Oyedokun, G.E., (2023). Evaluating the influence of Electronic Governance on Public Services Delivery in Nigeria. *Journal of Public Administration and Social Welfare Research*, 8(1). DOI: 10.56201/jpaswr.v8.no1.2023.pg1.15. 10.56201/jpaswr www.iiardjournals.org

- Ahmed, P. K., & Rafiq, M. (2003). Internal marketing issues and challenges. *European Journal of marketing*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/03090560310498813>
- Aljanabi, A. R. A. (2020). The role of innovation capability in the relationship between marketing capability and new product development: evidence from the telecommunication sector. *European Journal of Innovation Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJIM-04-2020-0146>
- Bardai, B., 2013. The Role of Organizational Culture in Organizational Innovation in Higher Education Institutions—A Study of Libyan Public Universities. *Al-Madinah Management and Finance Science*, 2 (1).
- Caka, N. & Erturk, A. (2010). Comparing innovation capability of small and medium size enterprise: examining the effects of organisational culture and empowerment. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 48 (3), 325-359. [doi/abs/10.1111/j.1540-627X.2010.00297.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-627X.2010.00297.x)
- Cameron, K.S. & Quinn, R.E. (1999). *Diagnosing and Changing Organizational Culture. Based on the Competing Values Framework*, Addison-Wesley, Reading, MA.
- Cerovic, Z., Kvasic, S. G., and Cerovic, M., 2010. The impact of national culture on the hotel organizational culture. *Managing Sustainability. Proceedings of the 12th International Conference, Portoroz, 23–26, November*. University of Primorska, Faculty of Management Koper.
- Dikmen, F., & Bozdağlar, H. (2017). The role of service culture in hospitality industry. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 8(5), 85-98.
- Do Khoi Nguyen, L. B. P., & Hui, L. (2019). Creating competitive advantage for vietnamese manufacturing and service firms: The role of collaborative culture and innovation capability. *International Journal of Business Administration*, 10(2). <https://doi.org/10.5430/ijba.v10n2p32>
- Gronroos, C. (1990). Relationship approach to marketing in service contexts: The marketing and organizational behavior interface. *Journal of business research*, 20(1), 3-11. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0148-2963\(90\)90037-E](https://doi.org/10.1016/0148-2963(90)90037-E)
- Heskett, J. L., Jones, T. O., Loveman, G. W., Sasser, W. E., & Schlesinger, L. A. (1994). Putting the service-profit chain to work. *Harvard business review*, 72(2), 164-174.
- Hogan, S. J., Soutar, G. N., McColl-Kennedy, J. R., & Sweeney, J. C. (2011). Reconceptualising professional service firm innovation capability: Scale development. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 40 (8), 1264-1273. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indmarman.2011.10.002>
- Howard, L. W. (1998). Validating the competing values model as a representation of organizational cultures. *International Journal of Organizational Analysis*, 6 (3), 231-250. <https://doi.org/10.1108/eb028886>
- Idiegbeyan-Ose, J., Opeke, R., & Nwokeoma, N. M. (2018). Influence of organisational culture on turnover intention of library staff in private university libraries, South-West Nigeria. *Academy of Strategic Management Journal*, 17(4).
- Imron, M. A., Munawaroh, U. I., Farida, R. D. M., Paramarta, V., Sunarsi, D., Akbar, I. R., ... & Masriah, I. (2021). Effect of organizational culture on innovation capability employees in the

- knowledge sharing perspective: Evidence from digital industries. *Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology*, 4189-4203.
- Lawson, B., & Samson, D. (2001). Developing innovation capability in organisations: a dynamic capabilities approach. *International Journal of Innovation Management*, 5 (3), 377-400. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S1363919601000427>
- Lillis, B., Szwejczewski, M., & Goffin, K. (2015). The development of innovation capability in services: research propositions and management implications. *Operations Management Research*, 8(1-2), 48–68. doi:10.1007/s12063-015-0099-z
- Luk, S. T. (1997). An examination of the role of marketing culture in service quality. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09596119710157522>
- March-Chorda, I. S. I. D. R. E., & Moser, J. E. F. F. (2011). How organisational culture affects innovation in large sized ict firms: a pilot study. In OLKC Congress.
- Marcoulides, G. A. & Heck, R. H. (1993). Organizational culture and performance: Proposing and testing a model. *Organization science*, 4 (2), 209-225. <https://doi.org/10.1287/orsc.4.2.209>
- Martin, J. (1992). *Cultures in organizations: Three perspectives*. Oxford University Press.
- Martins, E. C., & Terblanche, F. (2003). Building organisational culture that stimulates creativity and innovation. *European Journal of Innovation Management*, 6 (1), 64-74. <https://doi.org/10.1108/14601060310456337>
- Martins, E., & Martins, N. (2002). An Organisational Culture Model to Promote Creativity and Innovation, *Journal of Industrial Psychology*, 28 (4), 58-65.
- Mohammed, A., and Bardia, B., 2012. The Role of Organizational Culture in Organizational Innovation in Higher Education Institutions – A Study of Libyan Public Universities. *Australian Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, 6 (5), 175-184.
- Motilewa, B. D., Worlu, R. E., Agboola, G. M., & Adeniji, C. G. (2016). The role of organizational culture in achieving corporate objectives evidence from Covenant University, Nigeria. *Covenant Journal of Business and Social Sciences*, 7(2).
- Naranjo-Valencia, J. C., Jiménez-Jiménez, D., & Sanz-Valle, R. (2016). Studying the links between organizational culture, innovation, and performance in Spanish companies. *Revista Latinoamericana de Psicología*, 48(1), 30-41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rlp.2015.09.009>
- Obenchain, A., & Johnson, W. (2004). Product and process innovation in service organizations: The influence of organisations. *Journal of Applied Management and Entrepreneurship*, 9 (3), 91-113.
- Oney-Yazici, E., Giritli, H., Topcu-Oraz, G., & Acar, E. (2007). Organizational culture: the case of Turkish construction industry. *Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management*, 14 (6), 519-531. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09699980710828996>
- Oreagba, O.T, Ogunnaike, O., Igbadumhe, A. F., & Oranusi, C. (2023). Examining the moderators of innovation capability and firm performance: A Meta-Analytical Evidence. *International Journal of Management Leadership and Productivity Development*, 1(1), 137-152.
- Oyedokun, G.E. & Adeolu-Akande, M.A. (2022). Impact of Information Communication

- Technology (ICT) on Quality Education in Nigerian Tertiary Institutions. *Himalayan Journal of Economics and Business Management*, 3(2), 49-58 Available at: www.himjournals.com/article/articleID=610
- Pan Africa Capital, (2013). Telecommunications Industry in Nigeria: a decade of phenomenal growth and investment potentials. Nigeria: Pan Africa capital PLC.
- Rangone, A. (1999). A resource-based approach to strategy analysis in small-medium sized enterprises. *Small Business Economics*, 12 (3), 233-248.
- Rezaei, A., Allameh, S. M., & Ansari, R. (2018). Effect of organisational culture and organisational learning on organisational innovation: an empirical investigation. *International Journal of Productivity and Quality Management*, 23(3), 307-327. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJPQM.2018.089803>
- Saunila, M. (2020). Innovation capability in SMEs: A systematic review of the literature. *Journal of Innovation & Knowledge*, 5(4), 260-265. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jik.2019.11.002>
- Saunila, M., & Ukko, J. (2012). A conceptual framework for the measurement of innovation capability and its effects. *Baltic Journal of Management*, 7 (4), 355-375.
- Schein, E. (1990). Organizational Culture. *American Psychologist*, 45 (2), 109-119.
- Szydło, J., & Grześ-Bukłaho, J. (2020). Relations between National and Organisational Culture— Case Study. *Sustainability*, 12(4), 1522. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12041522>
- Tian, M., Deng, P., Zhang, Y., & Salmador, M. P. (2018). How does culture influence innovation? A systematic literature review. *Management Decision*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MD-05-2017-0462>. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MD-05-2017-0462>
- Valencia, J. C. N., Valle, R. S., & Jiménez, D. J. (2010). Organizational culture as determinant of product innovation. *European Journal of Innovation Management*, 13 (4), 466-480. <https://doi.org/10.1108/14601061011086294>
- Vincent, L. H., Bharadwaj, S. G., and Challagalla, G. N., 2004. Does innovation mediate firm performance? A meta-analysis of determinants and consequences of organizational innovation.
- Webster, C. (1990). Toward the measurement of the marketing culture of a service firm. *Journal of business research*, 21(4), 345-362. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0148-2963\(90\)90021-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0148-2963(90)90021-5)
- Yang, Z., Nguyen, V. T., & Le, P. B. (2018). Knowledge sharing serves as a mediator between collaborative culture and innovation capability: empirical research. *Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JBIM-10-2017-0245>
- Zerbe, W. J., Dobni, D., & Harel, G. H. (1998). Promoting employee service behaviour: The role of perceptions of human resource management practices and service culture. *Canadian Journal of Administrative Sciences/Revue Canadienne des Sciences de l'Administration*, 15(2), 165-179. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1936-4490.1998.tb00160.x>
- Zhang, M., & Hartley, J. L. (2018). Guanxi, IT systems, and innovation capability: The moderating role of proactiveness. *Journal of Business Research*, 90, 75-86. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2018.04.036>